

LIFETIME PREDICTIONS FOR POLYMERS AND COMPOSITES UNDER CONSTANT LOAD *

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A method is derived for estimating the lifetime of engineering polymers and composites acted upon by steady loads. The method applies a recently developed theory of crack growth in polymers. The basic properties that enter the analysis are the viscoelastic creep function of the material and the energy content of the crack-generated surface layer. In addition, the characteristic (failure) dimension of the body must be specified, together with the load (stress) level acting upon the body and a stress-distribution parameter. The final result of the derivation is a single, simple formula that expresses time-to-failure as a function of the input parameters. The method has been compared with experimental data upon aramid composite-material strands, with encouraging results. The resulting predictions are fundamentally different from those of the Zhurkov formula, which is based upon an activation-energy characterization for molecular schism. The model has been cast into a statistical form to accommodate a realistic treatment of data having wide scatter.

* This work was performed under the auspices of the U. S. Department of Energy by the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under contract No. W-7405-ENG-48.